

USING CLIL APPROACH WITH HISTORY STUDENTS

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With CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), students learn various subjects like history, art, science and math in a foreign language. Rather than being a stand-alone subject, language becomes a skill acquired in the classroom while mastering other types of content. It makes language relevant and meaningful in a way that few other methods can, and it strengthens the connections among various content area subjects. According to D. Marsh, "CLIL refers to situations where subjects, or parts of subjects, are taught through a foreign language with dual focused aims, namely the learning of content and the simultaneous learning of a foreign language". This article describes CLIL lesson used with 2 year ESP (history) students. According to the syllabus for history department students there is a topic "The Romans and Christians: Our Roman Heritage" and with the help of this topic students should develop vocabulary, ability to read the text in order to take input, also develop their collaborating and transferable skills.

History students in CLIL programmes have to know the academic language that learners need in order to communicate their knowledge of historical events, their ideas about chronology and their descriptions of the features of a particular period of time. Learners also need to be able to discuss historical arguments and justify their opinions. In order to achieve competence in communicating ideas about history, teachers should help learners notice key grammatical patterns as well as key content vocabulary.

We suggest to begin the lesson with "Activating prior knowledge" activity in order to find out what learners already know about the history topic. Learners may know many facts about a topic in their mother language, but may have difficulty in explaining this knowledge in a foreign language. That's why it is better to encourage them to use some L1 in this activity and then translate into English. Learners first look at the map on "Expansion of Rome on the Italian Peninsula" and identify the

areas controlled by Rome in 380 B.C., areas controlled by Carthage, areas added to Roman territory by 290 B.C., by 283 B.C., by 272 B.C.

Then we asked learners to tell any word or phrases they associate with the names of people. For example: Pompey, Caesar, Mark Antony, Hannibal, Cicero, Marcus Aurelius, Cleopatra, Octavian, Antony, Lepidus. After it we asked learners to predict what they will learn about in this lesson.

In the next activity teacher should pay attention to vocabulary of the theme. Learners need to produce the academic register of history and they need to know both content-obligatory (subject-specific language, grammatical structures, functional expressions: f.ex. plebeians, patricians, phalanx, dictator, praetors, magistrate, triumvirs, legion, censor, consul, maniples,) and content-compatible language (non-subject-specific language which learners may have learned in their English classes and use to communicate more fully about the curricular subject: f.ex. democracy, monarchy, republic, assembly).

Activity 3 aimed to elicit learners' opinions about the period looking at the picture and caption. Learners answer the following questions

- 1) How did Rome's geography contribute to its expansion?
- 2) Should a historian accept the story of Romulus and Remus as true? Were they the founders of Rome? Give reasons for your answer.
- 3) Why was Rome described as a republic but not a democracy?
- 4) How did the Twelve Tables help make Rome more democratic?

Learners check their answer with the information in the handout given by the teacher.

In the next activity learners are divided into groups and asked to tell about the wars happened at that time in Rome (Punic Wars, Macedonian Wars, Gallic Wars, Fall of Rome), the reasons and results of them. We also included collaborative tasks as they involve learners to produce key subject-specific vocabulary and structures in meaningful pair and group work activities. Activities support processing of new history content and language.

As a home task there given the tasks which require from learners analyzing, researching, collaborating and creating skills. Below are the tasks.

Group 1. Learners prepare a report on the topic "Caesar: Hero or Scoundrel".

Group 2. Take a photograph of those buildings in your community that appear to have been influenced by Roman architecture. Bring your pictures to the class and explain why you see Roman architectural influence.

Group 3. Prepare a “Meet the Press” program in which reporters interview Marcus Aurelius. What questions would the reporters ask? What answers do you think they might get?.

We think that learners usually need considerable support to develop their thinking skills in a non-native language. They need to communicate not only the everyday functional language practiced in many English classes, but they also need to communicate the cognitive, academic language of subjects. That’s why in the lessons the students should meet the cognitively challenging materials. We need to ask questions which encourage lower order thinking skills(what, when, where, which questions) and higher order thinking skills(why and how questions). While designing our lesson plan we take into consideration this principle.

At the end of the lesson we suggest to review what was learned. Teachers should ask students to tell something new they learned, something they already knew, something that was interesting, something they would like to find out about.

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